

Sample List

Sample Name

S1

S2

S3

S4

Sample S1

miRNA

sly-MIR156b 1327

sly-MIR1919a 1291

sly-MIR5304 8

sly-MIR395a 0

sly-MIR156c 179

Sample S2

miRNA

sly-MIR156b 214

sly-MIR5304 9

sly-MIR395a 20

sly-MIR156c 2509

sly-MIR167 1950

Sample S3

miRNA

sly-MIR169d 0

sly-MIR156b 4000

sly-MIR1919a 65

sly-MIR5304 18

sly-MIR395a 3

Sample S4

miRNA

sly-MIR169d 4

sly-MIR156b 4600

sly-MIR5304 14

sly-MIR1919a 97

sly-MIR395a 6

hairpin detail for S1

>sly-MIR156b

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCACGAAUAAUGAGGUGCUAAUUGGAAGCUGCACCUUA

AUCCUUGUGAUCUCUAUACUUCUGUCAU

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCAC*****

***** sly-miR156b

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S1_2126291_928_48.11	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGC.....	308
S1_1322819_308_15.97	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATT.....	38
S1_1027561_38_1.97	
.ACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA.....	24
S1_976006_24_1.24	
GACAGAAGATAGAGAGC.....	8
S1_2077205_8_0.41	
GACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA.....	7
S1_1999146_7_0.36	
...AGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....	3
S1_425906_3_0.16	
.TTACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....	3
S1_200479_3_0.16	
.TTTACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA.....	2
S1_963816_2_0.10	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGTT.....	2
S1_739479_2_0.10	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACGTA.....	1
S1_1037529_1_0.05	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATT.....	1
S1_936837_1_0.05	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATC.....	1
S1_1043316_1_0.05	
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATCT.....	1
S1_979968_1_0.05	

>sly-MIR1919a

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 CUAAGUCUAAUUAAUUUGAAUCAAUGUGGUAGGACGAGAGUCAUCUGUGACAGG
 AUUAUGGAAGAU

*****ACGAGAGUCAUCUGUGACAGG***** sly-miR1919a

.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGACAG.....

.. 1139S1_606732_1139_59.05

.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGACAG.....

152 S1_1468862_152_7.88

>sly-MIR5304

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 AACUUUCAUCUCACGUUCAAAAGAUGAAAGUUUAUAGAGAUGAGUAUGGUGCAUUG

GAUGUGUGGCCAUACCAUGGGUGAUGUUAGA

*****UCAAUGCUACAUACUCAUCCC*****

***** sly-

miR5304

.....TCAATGCTACATACTCATCCC.....

..... 4 S1_838321_4_0.21

.....CAATGCTACATACTCATCC.....

..... 2 S1_234249_2_0.10

.....TCAATGCTACATACTCA.....

..... 2 S1_764533_2_0.10

>sly-MIR395a

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UGACUUUGAAAAUUACGCAAACAAGUAUAUAAAUGCAUGAGUACGUAUUAGCU
AAAGAUGAUGAGUACAAUAUUGAUUCAUGUACCUUUGGAGUUCUUGACCACUU
CAUGAGAGCUAAUAUUUGAUUGUUUGAAGUCCU

*****CUGAAGUGUUUGGGGGAACUCC*****

***** sly-miR395a

>sly-MIR156c

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCACGAAUACGAGGUGCUAAUUGGAACAUGCACCUUA
AUUCUUUGUGCUCUCAUUCUUUUGUCAU

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCAC*****

***** sly-miR156c

TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 73

S1_1078378_73_3.78

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATTT..... 25

S1_511691_25_1.30

..CAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 19

S1_1451985_19_0.98

TGACAGAAGATAGAGA..... 17 S1_1153126_17_0.88

.ACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 13

S1_1445613_13_0.67

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCT..... 6 S1_40554_6_0.31

TGACAGAAGATAGAGAG..... 6

S1_259858_6_0.31

TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGC..... 5

S1_1722882_5_0.26

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATTCT..... 3

S1_79034_3_0.16

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATT..... 3

S1_1027962_3_0.16

GACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 2

S1_145757_2_0.10
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACG..... 2
 S1_776637_2_0.10
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCTTT..... 2
 S1_203983_2_0.10
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGT..... 1
 S1_1416954_1_0.05
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATCTTT..... 1
 S1_661423_1_0.05
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATTTC..... 1
 S1_2045310_1_0.05
 hairpin detail for S2

>sly-MIR156b

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 UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCAC*****
 ***** sly-miR156b
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAG..... 162
 S2_1925493_162_6.12
 TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....20
 S2_1991966_20_0.76
 .ACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA..... 15
 S2_1802451_15_0.57
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATT..... 10
 S2_1897394_10_0.38
 .ACAGAAGATAGAGAGC..... 4
 S2_1437373_4_0.15
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGTT..... 2
 S2_1485355_2_0.08
 TGACAGAAGATAGAGAG..... 1
 S2_480390_1_0.04

>sly-MIR5304

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 GAUGUGUGGCCAUACCAUGGGUGAUGUUAGA
 *****UCAAUGCUACAUACUCAUCCC*****
 ***** sly-
 miR5304
TCAATGCTACATACTCATCCC.....
 4 S2_1547575_4_0.15
TTCAATGCTACATACTCATCC.....

..... 2 S2_1667322_2_0.08
CAATGCTACATACTCATCCC.....
 2 S2_1746782_2_0.08
TCAATGCTACATACTCA.....
 1 S2_1411752_1_0.04
 >sly-MIR395a

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 AAAGAUGAUGAGUACAAUAUUGAUUCAUGUACCUUUGGAGUUCUUUGACCACUU
 CAUGAGAGCUAAUAUUUGAUUGUUUGAAGUCCU
 *****CUGAAGUGUUUGGGGGAACUCC*****

 ***** sly-miR395a

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CTGAAGTGTGGGGGAACTC.....
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 >sly-MIR156c

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 AUUCUUUGUGCUCUCAUUCUUUUGUCAU
 UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCAC*****
 ***** sly-miR156c

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....1584
 S2_545417_1584_59.86
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGA..... 609
 S2_1843459_609_23.01
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAG..... 143 S2_963808_143_5.40
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGC..... 137
 S2_443118_137_5.18
 ..CAGAAGATAGAGAGCA.....11 S2_283069_11_0.42
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAT..... 5
 S2_1028810_5_0.19
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATTT..... 5
 S2_945286_5_0.19
 .ACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 5
 S2_669436_5_0.19
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACT..... 4
 S2_1565079_4_0.15
 TGACAGAAGATAGAGA..... 3 S2_128716_3_0.11
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACG..... 1
 S2_1434094_1_0.04
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCATC..... 1

S2_1926692_1_0.04
 TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGTTTTTC..... 1
 S2_1661428_1_0.04
 >sly-MIR167

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 CAAAUUAAUUCGAGGAAAGAUCAGAUCAUGUGGCAGCCUUACCUGUCA AUGCCA
 UCACGA
 *****UGAAGCUGCCAGCAUGAUCUA*****
 ***** sly-miR167

.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 681
 S2_113341_681_25.73
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 526
 S2_1256569_526_19.88
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATC..... 240
 S2_1639444_240_9.07
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGA..... 199
 S2_1630663_199_7.52
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATG..... 145
 S2_1588658_145_5.48
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGAT..... 35
 S2_422048_35_1.32
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAA.....
 34 S2_901419_34_1.28
TTAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 16
 S2_518537_16_0.60
TTAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 14
 S2_449647_14_0.53
AAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAAAC.....
 6 S2_1136177_6_0.23
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTT..... 6
 S2_1892130_6_0.23
AAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 5
 S2_1521773_5_0.19
TTAAGCTGCCAGCATGATC..... 4
 S2_1974130_4_0.15
AGCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 3
 S2_569704_3_0.11
AAGCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 3
 S2_59906_3_0.11
TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATTT..... 3
 S2_984458_3_0.11
CTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 2
 S2_33918_2_0.08

.....GCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 2
S2_1174418_2_0.08
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTTTTTA.....
2 S2_962977_2_0.08
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAAAC.....
2 S2_996459_2_0.08
.....GGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 2
S2_1226626_2_0.08
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAAACT.....
2 S2_1141778_2_0.08
.....TTAAGCTGCCAGCATGAT..... 2
S2_996283_2_0.08
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATT..... 1
S2_1785792_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGAC..... 1
S2_1588002_1_0.04
.....GGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAA.....
1 S2_1519656_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTTT.....
1 S2_345262_1_0.04
.....AAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAAA..... 1
S2_663927_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTTATTT.....
1 S2_635059_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAAAT.....
1 S2_38805_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAAATT.....
1 S2_64435_1_0.04
.....AGCTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 1
S2_881177_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATTTC..... 1
S2_996728_1_0.04
.....GAAGCTGCCAGCATGA..... 1
S2_104166_1_0.04
.....AAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTAA..... 1
S2_127790_1_0.04
.....GGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 1
S2_594750_1_0.04
.....GTAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCT..... 1
S2_1502290_1_0.04
.....TGAAGCTGCCAGCATGATCA..... 1
S2_854190_1_0.04
.....GCTGCCAGCATGATCTA..... 1
S2_1201638_1_0.04

hairpin detail for S3

>sly-MIR169d

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GCCUACUUCUUUGAUUAUAUAGUUUAAAAUAAUAAUUAUUGACAAUAAUUGUCAUU
UGGUCGUAGGCAAGUUAUCCUGGCUAUCUUGACAUGCUCGUAUUUUUCAUGUAA
GACCUUAUCUUC

*****UAGCCAAGGAUGACUUGCCUA*****

***** sly-miR169d

>sly-MIR156b

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCACGAAUAAUGAGGUGCUAAUUGGAAGCUGCACCUUA
AUUCCUUGUGAUCUCUAUACUUCUGUCAU

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCAC*****
***** sly-miR156b

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....	2185	
S3_440494_2185_139.73		
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA.....	1734	
S3_1181938_1734_110.89		
TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....	34	
S3_1611231_34_2.17		
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACT.....	17	
S3_1265636_17_1.09		
.ACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA.....	9	
S3_1457679_9_0.58		
TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGA.....	6	
S3_104046_6_0.38		
..CAGAAGATAGAGAGCACT.....	3	
S3_703730_3_0.19		
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATTT.....	2	
S3_764157_2_0.13		
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCT.....	2	S3_60754_2_0.13
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAT.....	2	
S3_832027_2_0.13		
TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATT.....	2	
S3_1534681_2_0.13		
...AGAAGATAGAGAGCAC.....	2	
S3_636636_2_0.13		
TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACGAAT.....	1	
S3_638049_1_0.06		
TGACAGAAGATAGAGAG.....	1	
S3_388189_1_0.06		

>sly-MIR1919a

AUCUCCGGUAGUCCUGUCGCAGAUGACUCUCGAUCUUGUCAUUAAGCCCCUUUCU
CUAAGUCUAAUUAAUUUGAAUUCAAUGUGGUAGGACGAGAGUCAUCUGUGACAGG
AUUAUGGAAGAU

*****ACGAGAGUCAUCUGUGACAGG***** sly-miR1919a

.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGACAG.....

48 S3_575932_48_3.07

.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGACAGGA.....

.... 16 S3_130600_16_1.02

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..... 1 S3_263680_1_0.06

>sly-MIR5304

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AACUUUCAUCUCACGUUCAAAAGAUGAAAGUUUAUAGAGAUGAGUAUGGUGCAUUG
GAUGUGUGGCCAUACCAUGGGUGAUGUUAGA

*****UCAAUGCUCACAUCUCAUCCC*****

***** sly-

miR5304

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..... 15 S3_1251218_15_0.96

.....TTCAATGCTACATACTCATCC.....

..... 2 S3_1348483_2_0.13

.....TCAATGCTACATACTCATCC.....

..... 1 S3_1202818_1_0.06

>sly-MIR395a

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AAAGAUGAUGAGUACAAUAUUGAUUCAUGUACCUUUGGAGUUCUCCUUGACCACUU
CAUGAGAGCUAAUAUUUGAUUGUUUGAAGUCCU

*****CUGAAGUGUUUGGGGGAACUCC*****

***** sly-miR395a

.....AGTGTTTGGGGGAAC.....

..... 1 S3_340504_1_0.06

.....CTGAAGTGTTTGGGGGA.....

..... 1 S3_509299_1_0.06

.....CTGAAGTGTTTGGGGGAAC.....

..... 1 S3_953560_1_0.06

hairpin detail for S4

>sly-MIR169d

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GCCUACUUCAUUUGAUUAUAGUUUAAAAUAAUAAUUAUUGACAAUUAUUUGUCAUU
UGGUCGUAGGCAAGUUAUCCUGGCUAUCUUGACAUGCUCGUAUUUUUCAUGUAA
GACCUUAUCUUC

*****UAGCCAAGGAUGACUUGCCUA*****

***** sly-miR169d

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..... 4 S4_117857_4_0.27

>sly-MIR156b

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AUUCCUUGUGAUCUCUAUACUUCUGUCAU

UUGACAGAAGAUAGAGAGCAC*****

***** sly-miR156b

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 3595

S4_462254_3595_238.31

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGA..... 668

S4_1559828_668_44.28

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGC..... 259

S4_375589_259_17.17

TGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCA..... 38

S4_685864_38_2.52

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCACT..... 15

S4_1324818_15_0.99

.ACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 7

S4_567516_7_0.46

TGACAGAAGATAGAGA..... 6

S4_109057_6_0.40

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGATT..... 5

S4_1605847_5_0.33

TGACAGAAGATAGAGAG..... 2

S4_407127_2_0.13

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCTTT..... 1

S4_319154_1_0.07

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGCTT.....1

S4_1563700_1_0.07

.TTTACAGAAGATAGAGAGCAC..... 1

S4_1621175_1_0.07

TTGACAGAAGATAGAGAGT..... 1

S4_873927_1_0.07

..CAGAAGATAGAGAGCACT..... 1

S4_737528_1_0.07
>sly-MIR5304

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AACUUUCAUCUCACGUUCAAAAGAUGAAAGUUUAUAGAGAUGAGUAUGGUGCAUUG
GAUGUGUGGCCAUACCAUGGGUGAUGUUAGA
*****UCAAUGCUACAUAUCUCAUCCC*****
***** sly-
miR5304

.....TCAATGCTACATACTCATCCC.....
..... 12 S4_1309907_12_0.80
.....TTCAATGCTACATACTCATCC.....
..... 2 S4_1411075_2_0.13
>sly-MIR1919a

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CUAAGUCUAAUUAAUUUGAAUUCUAAUGUGGUAGGACGAGAGUCAUCUGUGACAGG
AUUAUGGAAGAU

*****ACGAGAGUCAUCUGUGACAGG***** sly-miR1919a

.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGACAGGA.....
... 33 S4_137060_33_2.19
.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGA.....
25 S4_1606844_25_1.66
.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTGACA.....
20 S4_119176_20_1.33
.....CGAGAGTCATCTGTGACAGGA.....
.. 17 S4_1582327_17_1.13
.....AGGACGAGAGTCATCTGTGA.....
1 S4_1465708_1_0.07
.....ACGAGAGTCATCTGTG..... 1
S4_311946_1_0.07

>sly-MIR395a

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UGACUUUGAAAUAUACGCAAACAAGUAUAUAUAAAUGCAUGAGUACGUAAUAGCU
AAAGAUGAUGAGUACAAUAUUGAUUCAUGUACCUUUGGAGUUCUUUGACCACUU
CAUGAGAGCUAAUAUUUGAUUGUUUGAAGUCCU
*****CUGAAGUGUUUGGGGGAACUCC*****
***** sly-miR395a

.....CTGAAGTGTTTGGGGGAAC.....
..... 4 S4_1401870_4_0.27
.....CTGAAGTGTTTGGGGGA.....

